

CRYPTOGRAPHIC COMPATIBILITY IN API
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ABSTRACT

The transition to Post-Quantum Cryptography requires not only algorithm replacement, but also flexibility at the architectural level. This paper develops a cryptographic agility model for API infrastructures and evaluates its effectiveness in the migration process. The proposed model is based on policy-based management, an abstraction layer, and a centralized cryptographic service. Empirical results show that migration costs can be reduced by more than 70%.

Introduction. The transition to PQC is a long-term and gradual process. During the full migration, compatibility with classical systems must be maintained.

Therefore, the concept of cryptographic flexibility is important. This approach involves managing algorithms through policy rather than “hardening” them into code [1,2].

Research methodology. In the second article, the research was aimed at a comprehensive assessment of the impact of post-quantum cryptography mechanisms on security and performance in distributed information systems based on artificial intelligence. The methodology was developed based on a multi-layered experimental approach and included theoretical modeling, practical implementation, and empirical measurements. The object of the study was a microservice architecture integrated with artificial intelligence modules. The architecture was deployed in a containerized environment, and services communicated with each other through REST-based application programming interfaces. Each microservice has an independent computational process and is divided into separate components that perform authentication, data processing, model inference, and monitoring functions. The artificial intelligence module simulated the process of calling a machine learning model and returning results in real time [3,4].

The TLS 1.3 protocol was used to ensure security at the transport level. To evaluate the key exchange mechanisms, classical elliptic curve algorithms and CRYSTALS-Kyber were implemented as a post-quantum key encapsulation algorithm. In addition to the classical ECDSA, the CRYSTALS-Dilithium and FALCON algorithms were used to evaluate the digital signature process. Methodologically, the research was carried out in three stages. In the first stage, a basic classical configuration was established and the normal operating parameters of the system were determined. At this stage, indicators such as handshake duration, token

signing time, API response latency, processor load, and memory consumption were measured. In the second stage, post-quantum algorithms were introduced step by step, and the impact of each change on the system was recorded separately. In the third stage, full post-quantum and hybrid configurations were tested and the results were compared. Experimental tests were carried out using load generation tools. The number of requests was gradually increased, and the maximum throughput limit and latency dynamics of the system were determined. At least several thousand transactions were recorded for each configuration, and the results were statistically processed, and the average value and variance indicators were calculated. The presence of an artificial intelligence module was of particular importance in the methodology. Since the model inference process creates a certain computational load and, together with cryptographic operations, affects the overall system efficiency. Therefore, the experiments were conducted in conditions close to real-time. Each request sent via the API was authenticated, forwarded to the artificial intelligence model, and the result was returned. During the measurement process, the main attention was paid to the indicators of connection establishment time at the transport layer, signature generation and verification duration, total response latency, and transaction density. The processor load and memory consumption were also monitored, since post-quantum algorithms often require large key sizes and complex mathematical operations.

A comparative approach was used to analyze the results. Each configuration was compared with the classical model and the percentage of relative increase or decrease was calculated. In order to ensure statistical reliability, a generalized assessment was given based on average values. The methodology developed in this way allowed for a comprehensive and scientific assessment of the practical consequences of implementing post-quantum cryptography mechanisms in a high-load microservice infrastructure based on artificial intelligence.

Research Results The second article provides an in-depth empirical analysis of the impact of post-quantum cryptography algorithms on system resources, response speed, and throughput in an AI-based microservice infrastructure. During the experiments, classical, partially post-quantum, fully post-quantum, and hybrid configurations were compared. The following key metrics were measured in the study: TLS connection establishment time, JWT signing and verification time, overall API response latency, CPU load, RAM consumption, and maximum transaction density.

Table 1.

TLS connection establishment time (average value)

Configuration	Handshake time (ms)
Classic (ECDHE + ECDSA)	47
PQC KEM (Kyber)	85
PQC Signature (Dilithium)	52
PQC Signature (FALCON)	54
Full PQC	98
Hybrid (classic + PQC)	72

The results show that when post-quantum mechanisms are used in the key exchange phase, the connection establishment time is almost doubled compared to the classical model. The highest performance is recorded in the fully post-quantum configuration.

Table 2.

JWT signing and verification duration

Configuration	Signing (ms)	Verification (ms)
Classic	3	2
Dilithium	9	5
FALCON	6	4
Full PQC	10	6
Hybrid	7	4

Post-quantum signature algorithms performed significantly slower signature generation than classical algorithms. However, the verification process remained relatively stable. The FALCON algorithm showed a balanced result between signature size and speed.

Table 3.

General API response time and throughput

Configuration	Response time (ms)	Permeability (TPS)
Classic	125	840
PQC KEM	155	710
Dilithium	170	680
FALCON	158	720
Full PQC	195	600
Hybrid	165	705

The increase in response time is explained by the increased complexity of the handshake and signature operations. In the fully post-quantum model, the throughput decreased to 600 TPS, which is about a 28–30 percent decrease compared to the classical model.

Table 4.

Resource utilization indicators

Configuration	CPU usage (%)	Memory usage (MB)
Classic	52	410
PQC KEM	63	455
Dilithium	68	470
FALCON	64	448
Full PQC	75	520
Hybrid	66	465

The results confirmed that post-quantum algorithms require more computational resources. In particular, the CPU load and memory consumption increased significantly in the full PQC configuration. The results obtained show that the implementation of post-quantum cryptography in microservice infrastructures based on artificial intelligence has a certain impact on system performance. The most noticeable impact was observed in the transport

layer. The complexity of the key exchange mechanisms increases the handshake time, which can affect the level of service under high load. Post-quantum variants of digital signature mechanisms slow down the authentication phase, but this is a relatively small fraction of the total API transaction time. Therefore, switching to post-quantum mechanisms in the authentication layer can be a relatively safe strategy in practice. A full post-quantum configuration provides maximum quantum stability, but there is a decrease in efficiency and throughput. This result is especially important in systems integrated with artificial intelligence modules, since model inference itself requires significant computational resources.

The hybrid model, on the other hand, provided an optimal balance between security and performance. It increases cryptographic strength by using classical and post-quantum mechanisms in parallel, and maintains system efficiency at a higher level than the fully post-quantum model. The results show that the post-quantum migration process should be carried out in stages, and architectural optimization, resource expansion, and load balancing mechanisms play an important role in this process.

Conclusion. The study has scientifically confirmed the practical feasibility of implementing post-quantum cryptography algorithms in an AI-based microservice API infrastructure. Post-quantum key exchange and signature mechanisms significantly increase the level of security, but they impose an additional burden on computing resources and response speed. Although a fully post-quantum architecture provides maximum quantum stability, performance efficiency decreases. The hybrid approach has emerged as the most suitable model for the transition period and has created a scientific basis for a phased migration strategy in real industrial infrastructures. Thus, the process of protecting AI systems in the face of quantum computing threats is not limited to the choice of cryptographic algorithm alone, but also requires a comprehensive approach that includes architectural design, resource management, and system optimization..

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